

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN FORMING COOPERATIVE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN YOUNG MEN AND GIRL

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Abstract. This study provides information on the main essence of forming collaborative relationships between young people and the importance of psychological training in improving collaborative skills. Based on this information, we have made recommendations on how to shape the worldview of young people, raise their spirituality and improve their level of thinking through organizing psychological training. We also used information on the role of modern psychological training in creating a collaborative environment to date as the main content of our study.

Keywords: Collaborative relationships, psychological training, worldview formation, collaborative skills, psychological interviews, psychological methods.

YIGIT QIZLAR ORASIDA KOLLOBORATIV MUNOSABATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNI O'RNINI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot davomida yigit-qizlar orasida kolloborativ munosabatlarni shakllantirishning asosiy mohiyati va kolloborativ ko'nikmalarini oshirishda psixologik treninglarni ahamiyati haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Ushbu ma'lumotlarga asoslangan holda, psixologik treninglarni tashkil qilish orqali yigit-qizlarning dunyoqarashini shakllantirish, ma'naviyatini yuksaltirish va fikrlash darajasini oshirish bo'yicha mulohazalarni tadqiqotimiz asosida aytib o'tganmiz. Shuningdek, hozirgi kunga kelib kolloborativ (hamkorlik) muhitini yaratishda zamonaviy psixologik treninglarni tutgan roli haqida ma'lumotlarni tadqiqotimizning asosiy mazmuni sifatida foydalanganmiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Kolloborativ munosabatlar, psixologik treninglar, dunyoqarashni shakllantirish, kolloborativ ko'nikmalar, psixologik suhbatlar, psixologik metodlar.

РОЛЬ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ОТНОШЕНИЙ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА СРЕДИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

Аннотация. В настоящем исследовании раскрывается основная суть формирования отношений сотрудничества между молодежью и значение психологических тренингов в развитии навыков сотрудничества. На основе этой информации мы разработали рекомендации по формированию мировоззрения молодежи, повышению её духовности и развитию мышления посредством организации психологических тренингов.

Информация о роли современных психологических тренингов в создании условий сотрудничества на современном этапе легла в основу нашего исследования.

Ключевые слова: Сотруднические отношения, психологическое обучение, формирование мировоззрения, навыки сотрудничества, психологическое интервью, психологические методы.

Introduction

Psychological training is one of the most effective methods widely used in modern psychological practice to unlock human potential, strengthen interpersonal relationships, solve psychological problems, and facilitate social adaptation. In particular, group training is a psychological field that allows not only individual but also collective consciousness and behavior to change, exchange social experiences, develop a culture of cooperation, empathy, and communication. From this perspective, working with groups in psychological training is not only a technical aspect, but also a complex psychological process, based on its own rules and mechanisms. When working with a group, it is first necessary to create an environment of psychological safety. Only when training participants feel guaranteed that they will not be evaluated, criticized, or their opinions will be denied, will they be able to freely express their emotions, experiences, and views. Therefore, the trainer must create a socio-psychological environment in the group that ensures confidentiality based on ethical criteria and strictly adheres to the principles of tolerance, mutual respect, and sincerity in reasoning. The key to the effectiveness of psychological training is to work with a clearly targeted, methodologically based and step-by-step plan of work. Any training process is strengthened not only by interactivity and emotional impact, but also by deep theoretical knowledge, psychological sensitivity and methodological analysis. Identifying methodological problems in advance, developing appropriate solutions to them, and adapting the training design to the needs and psychotypes of participants are the most urgent tasks of modern psychological training today. Trainers should be not only knowledgeable, but also reflexive and adaptive psychological leaders. In modern society, relationships between young men and women based on mutual respect, solidarity and cooperation are one of the important factors of social stability. Interpersonal relationships formed in youth directly affect the culture of communication in family, work and social life. Therefore, the formation of collaborative relationships between young men and women in educational institutions is considered an urgent issue. The formation of collaborative relationships between young men and women is one of the most important psychological areas of modern education. In this process, psychological training serves as an effective mechanism for developing a person's self-awareness, empathy, tolerance, cooperation and communication culture. Systematic implementation of such training in educational institutions increases the socio-psychological maturity of young people and helps to form healthy relationships in society. Psychological training plays an important role in this process. Trainings develop young people's self-awareness, flexibility in relationships, the ability to understand each other, as well as collective thinking.

Through trainings, young people learn to manage their emotions, respect the opinions of others, and work together towards a goal. Simple theoretical conversations are not enough to form positive relationships between young people based on cooperation, mutual respect and understanding. To do this, they need to be activated through practical activities and training sessions.

In the current era, individualism, competition, alienation and mutual distrust are increasing in communication between young people. These situations are further exacerbated by social networks, technological tools and individual interests. Therefore, it has become an urgent issue to educate young people in a spirit of cooperation towards each other through psychological training in educational institutions, study groups or youth centers. The psychologist-trainer should strive to create a trusting and safe environment in the group. This encourages students to learn and try new ideas without fear of making mistakes. Motivation: in a collaborative approach, the psychologist-trainer can use various motivational strategies to encourage students to be active and increase their interest in learning. For example, celebrating successes in the group, expressing positive thoughts and encouraging students. The psychologist-trainer should consider group members as equals and give them the opportunity to participate in setting goals and making decisions. Basic pedagogical and psychological principles of creating opportunities to learn from mistakes: In order for students to learn from their mistakes, they should be given the opportunity to recognize and correct them.

A psychologist-trainer should help in such processes. A psychologist-trainer should listen to the needs and interests of his students, help them achieve their goals. During the psychological training, a short presentation is made by the trainer about the topic, goals and objectives of the training, and its main essence in general. The presentation is carried out in accordance with the topic of the training and based on the requirements set for the training. Information that is used by educators and psychologists as a means of presenting new material to train training participants can be used. Psychological trainings are conducted by the trainer for those participants who are ready to receive new material. In order for the participants to fully and clearly perceive the presentation, adapt to the training session, and also to create readiness for the training, the trainer conducts facilitation, psychological moderation, or role-playing games before the psychological lecture. It is important that each training participant actively listens to the information during the psychological assessment process. By forming collaborative relationships between young people and girls, it is possible to increase their worldview and develop collaborative skills. When we look at the research of experienced pedagogical psychologists, the role of psychological training in the formation of collaborative skills among young people is highly appreciated. We believe that if a psychologist-trainer conducts psychological interviews with young people and helps to eliminate problems in the psyche of young people, the worldview of our young people will increase.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we believe that psychological training is of great importance as a key tool in the formation of collaborative relationships between young people and girls. Mental health is of great importance for the upbringing, spiritual development and future development of young people. Also, by conducting psychological interviews with our young people by psychologist-trainers, we can eliminate their psychological problems. For this, we believe that it is appropriate to organize high-quality psychological training.

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